

Preference-Based Design and Prototype Development of Farm Clothing for Youth Farmers in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract: This study adopted a preference-based design approach to develop prototype farm clothing for youth farmers in Cross River State, Nigeria. A survey and research-and-development (R&D) design were employed. From a population of 1,471,967 youth farmers, a sample of 400 respondents was selected using a multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected using the Protective Clothing Needs Assessment Questionnaire (PCNAQ), which was validated by experts, with reliability established using Cronbach's alpha. Mean and standard deviation were used for data analysis. The findings identified 24 farming activities commonly performed by youth farmers and 14 functional clothing needs rated as important for farm work. Most proposed protective clothing design options were preferred, while a sleeveless apron and pleated nose mask fell below the acceptance benchmark and were excluded. Based on these preferences, prototype farm clothing items were developed in three size categories, including overalls (with and without hood), head protection, face masks, and gloves. The prototypes were assessed for fit and functional attributes by a panel of 15 judges. The study demonstrates how user-identified activities and preferences can be systematically translated into locally appropriate farm clothing prototypes.

Keywords: Farm clothing, Functional design, Preference-based design, Prototype development, Youth farmers

1. Introduction

Youth participation in agriculture has increased in Nigeria as a response to unemployment and limited formal-sector opportunities, particularly in rural communities (Oduwole and Adebisi, 2017). In Cross River State, youth farmers are actively engaged in pre-planting, planting, and post-planting activities within a humid tropical rainforest environment. These activities expose farmers to biological, chemical, and physical hazards associated with farming tools, agro-chemicals, insects, dense vegetation, and adverse weather conditions (Ayang, 2016; Etim et al., 2021). For the purpose of this study, youth refer to individuals aged 18–35 years who are actively engaged in farming activities in Cross River State.

Despite the intensity of farming operations, agricultural safety practices receive limited attention in the state (Ofem et al., 2021). Frequent use of fertilizers and pesticides has been linked to health challenges such as skin irritation and other adverse reactions (Effiong and Aboh, 2019), while reliance on conventional everyday clothing provides little functional protection during farm work (Etim et al., 2021). Although personal protective equipment exists, most options are imported, costly, poorly adapted to humid conditions, or inaccessible to small-scale youth farmers. Locally used alternatives rarely reflect task-specific or climate-appropriate design features.

Previous studies emphasize the importance of integrating user needs and activity requirements into functional clothing design (Azonuche, 2016; Kureave, 2016), yet empirical research on preference-based farm clothing tailored to youth farmers in Cross River State remains limited. This study addresses this gap by adopting a preference-based design approach to develop prototype farm clothing informed by user-identified activities and preferences, thereby contributing locally grounded design evidence for agricultural protective clothing development.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Youth farmers in Cross River State engage in largely manual farming activities such as land clearing, planting, weeding, fertilizer application, pesticide spraying, and harvesting within a humid rainforest environment that exposes them to environmental and occupational hazards. However, agricultural safety practices receive limited attention, and farmers commonly rely on conventional everyday clothing that offers minimal protection during farm work (Etim et al., 2021; Ofem et al., 2021). Frequent use of fertilizers and pesticides has been associated with health challenges including skin irritation and other adverse reactions, indicating continued exposure during routine farming activities (Effiong and Aboh, 2019). Although agricultural protective equipment exists, most available options are imported, costly, poorly adapted to local climatic conditions, or inaccessible to small-scale youth farmers. Furthermore, there is limited locally generated design evidence on farm clothing that reflects the specific activities, preferences, and environmental conditions of youth farmers in Cross River State.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to develop prototype farm clothing for youth farmers in farming communities in Cross River State using a preference-based design approach. Specifically, the study aimed to identify farming activities that influence clothing needs, determine functional protective clothing features preferred by youth farmers, and translate these preferences into the design and construction of farm clothing prototypes suitable for the local environment.

2. Methods and Materials

2.1. Research Design

The study adopted a survey design and a research and development (R&D) approach. The survey component was used to identify farming activities and protective clothing preferences of youth farmers, while the research-and-development component guided the systematic design and construction of prototype farm clothing based on the identified preferences.

2.2. Area of the Study

The study was conducted in Cross River State, Nigeria. The state was considered appropriate due to

the high level of youth involvement in farming activities and the prevalence of manual agricultural practices under humid tropical conditions.

2.3 Research and Development Procedure

The R&D process followed seven sequential stages:

1. Needs Assessment

A needs assessment was conducted using the Protective Clothing Needs Assessment Questionnaire (PCNAQ) to identify farming activities commonly performed by youth farmers, exposure-related concerns, and functional clothing requirements. The instrument captured clothing needs related to protection, comfort, ease of movement, durability, affordability, fastening, and adaptability to climatic conditions. Findings from this stage informed all subsequent design decisions.

2. Design Concept Development and Sketching

Based on identified activities and preferences, multiple clothing design concepts were developed and presented through sketches showing variations in garment type, coverage, protective accessories, and detachable components.

3. Selection of Design Concepts

Design concepts were reviewed and the most preferred options were selected using mean ratings obtained from the needs assessment. Designs with mean scores of 3.50 and above were considered acceptable and selected for prototype development.

4. Fabric and Material Selection

Fabric and materials were selected based on availability, durability, comfort, and suitability for the humid climatic conditions of Cross River State. Padding and detachable components were incorporated to enhance protection and adaptability.

5. Pattern Drafting and Sizing

Patterns were drafted using standard body measurements for small, medium, and large sizes to ensure proper fit, mobility, and ease of movement.

6. Prototype Construction

Selected designs were cut and sewn to produce prototype farm clothing items, including overalls (with

and without hoods), head protectors, face masks, and hand gloves.

7. Fitting, Assessment, and Revision

The prototypes were fitted and assessed by youth farmers and Home Economics experts for fit, comfort, and functionality. Feedback informed final adjustments before production.

2.4. Population for the Study

The population of the study consisted of 1,471,967 youth farmers aged 18–35 years in Cross River State. This figure was derived from the 2006 National Population Census and represents an estimated proportion of youths actively engaged in crop production and related agricultural activities in rural and peri-urban communities of the state. For the purpose of this study, youth farmers refer to young persons involved in farming activities within this age range. This population served as the basis for determining the sample size used in the study.

2.5. Sample and Sampling Techniques

A sample size of 400 youth farmers was selected from the population of 1,471,967 youth farmers in Cross River State. The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane formula for known populations (Uzoagulu, 2011). A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted to ensure coverage across different geographical zones of the state.

The sampling procedure was carried out in four stages:

Stage 1: Selection of Senatorial Zones - All three senatorial zones of Cross River State (Zones A, B, and C) were included to ensure statewide representation.

Stage 2: Selection of Local Government Areas (LGAs) - Four LGAs were purposively selected based on the intensity of farming activities and concentration of youth farmers. Calabar Municipality and Calabar South were selected from Zone A, while Ikom and Ogoja were selected from Zones B and C, respectively.

Stage 3: Selection of Communities - Farming communities within each selected LGA were identified in consultation with agricultural extension officers and community leaders, focusing on areas with active youth participation in farming.

Stage 4: Selection of Respondents - Within the selected communities, youth farmers were randomly selected using simple random sampling techniques until the required sample size of 400 respondents was achieved.

This multi-stage approach enhanced representativeness and reduced selection bias across different farming environments in Cross River State.

2.6. Instrument for Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled the Protective Clothing Needs Assessment Questionnaire (PCNAQ), developed in line with the objectives of the study. The instrument consisted of three sections. **Section A** collected demographic information, including location, age (18–35 years), educational qualification, and farming occupation. **Section B** contained 24 items on pre-planting, planting, and post-planting farming activities to identify tasks influencing clothing needs. **Section C** comprised 20 functional protective clothing design options presented as illustrated sketches, which respondents rated using a five-point Likert scale. Design options with mean scores of 3.50 and above were considered preferred and selected for prototype development.

2.7. Method of Data Analysis

Data obtained for the study were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Responses were rated on a five-point Likert scale coded as follows: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). A cut-off mean of 3.50 was adopted as the decision rule. This value represents the midpoint between Undecided (3.00) and Agree (4.00). Items with mean values of 3.50 and above were regarded as agreed/accepted, while items with mean values below 3.50 were regarded as not agreed/not accepted.

3. Result

Research Question 1: What are the farming activities carried out by youths that characterized their clothing needs in Cross River State

The results in Table 1 indicate that youth farmers in Cross River State engage in diverse pre-planting, planting, and post-planting activities, with all items recording mean values above the criterion mean of 3.50, confirming their relevance to clothing needs. Activities with the highest mean scores included weeding ($\bar{x} = 4.67$), site clearing ($\bar{x} = 4.60$), fertilizer application/manuring ($\bar{x} = 4.57$), harvesting ($\bar{x} = 4.56$), and pesticide spraying ($\bar{x} = 4.46$). These activities involve prolonged contact with vegetation, soil, tools, and agro-chemicals, indicating higher exposure levels. The ranking of activities therefore provides a basis for prioritizing functional clothing design features during prototype development.

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation ratings of respondents on farming activities carried out by youths that characterised their clothing needs in Cross River State

S/N	Various farming activities are performed by young farmers on the farm	N	Mean	S.D	Remarks
PRE-PLANTING OPERATION					
1	Seed Procurement	400	4.54	.75	A
2	Site Clearing	400	4.60	.69	A
3	Making Mounds	400	4.49	.73	A
4	Bush Burning	400	4.19	.95	A
5	Land Scaping	400	4.23	.82	A
6	Stumping	400	4.36	.80	A
7	Plotting	400	4.33	.79	A
8	Digging of Ground	400	4.35	.79	A
PLANTING OPERATIONS					
9	Seed Treatment	400	4.54	.66	A
10	Seed Sowing	400	4.46	.71	A
11	Planting Time	400	4.47	.75	A
12	Planting Space	400	4.52	.73	A
13	Planting Depth	400	4.50	.72	A
14	Transplanting	400	4.50	.73	A
15	Viability of Seed	400	4.47	.69	A
16	Cutting	400	4.42	.73	A
POST PLANTING OPERATIONS					
17	Weeding	400	4.67	.62	A
18	Trimming	400	4.46	.73	A
19	Mulching	400	4.56	.71	A
20	Fertiliser Operation/Manuring	400	4.57	.71	A
21	Pesticides Spraying	400	4.46	.72	A
22	Drying	400	4.18	.88	A
23	Harvesting	400	4.56	.76	A
24	Storage	400	4.50	.78	A

Key: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, U = Undecided, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree.

Research Question 2: What are the functional protective clothing needed by young farmers with respect to their activities in farming communities in Cross River State?

The results in Table 2 show that youth farmers in Cross River State identified several functional clothing characteristics as important needs, with all items recording mean values above the criterion mean of 3.50. Key needs included body coverage, secure fastening, durability, absorbency, ease of movement, temperature regulation, and affordability. These needs reflect common farming challenges such as exposure to insects, contact with vegetation, agro-chemical use, prolonged physical activity, and heat in a humid environment. The low variation in responses indicates shared experiences among respondents and supports the use of these attributes as a basis for prototype clothing development.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation ratings of respondents on the functional protective clothing needed by youth farmers with respect to their activities in farming communities in Cross River State

Functional Clothing need to:		N	Mean	S.D	Remarks
1	Protect wearer's head from harm	400	4.53	.69	A
2	Be safe for the wearer	400	4.52	.61	A
3	Fit a range of size	400	4.34	.75	A
4	Allow free movement in the farm	400	4.39	.76	A
5	Facilitate activity performance	400	4.46	.67	A
6	Have special closures such as Velcro	400	4.24	.76	A
7	Fit the wearer	400	4.23	.81	A
8	Allow easy donning and doffing (wearing and taking off)	400	4.40	.79	A
9	Have safe fastening	400	4.50	.70	A
10	Be affordable by young farmers	400	4.39	.82	A
11	Be durable and easy to care for	400	4.40	.78	A
12	Be absorbent	400	4.35	.77	A
13	Take care of temperature change	400	4.26	.78	A
14	Have danger signals	400	4.23	.83	A

Key: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, U = Undecided, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree.

Research Question 3: What are the functional protective clothing items preferred by the youths in farming communities in Cross River State?

The results in Table 3 show that most proposed functional clothing design options were preferred by respondents, as the majority recorded mean values of 3.50 and above. However, the apron without sleeve ($\bar{x} = 2.97$) and the pleated nose mask ($\bar{x} = 3.30$) fell below the acceptance threshold and were not preferred. These less acceptable options were therefore excluded from prototype development.

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation ratings of respondents on the functional protective clothing items preferred by the youths in farming communities in Cross River State.

S/N	Protective clothing items preferred by youth farmers.	N	Mean	S.D	Remarks
1.	Overall with hood	400	4.23	1.02	P
2.	Overall without hood	400	4.43	.86	P
3.	Overall, with short sleeves	400	3.56	.99	P
4.	Trouser with a waistband	400	3.96	.87	P
5.	Free trouser with rope at the waist	400	3.62	.94	P
6.	Trouser with elastic at the waist and ankle	400	3.86	.93	P
7.	Shirt with collar	400	3.58	1.09	P
8.	Jump suit with hood	400	3.79	1.15	P
9.	Jump suit without hood	400	3.89	.97	P
10	Apron with sleeve	400	3.73	1.05	P
11	Apron without sleeve	400	2.97	1.05	NP
12	Long gloves	400	4.22	.90	P
13	Short gloves	400	4.07	.81	P
14	Leather gloves	400	4.26	.81	P
15	Head protector with extension	400	4.17	.98	P
16	Face cape	400	3.61	1.09	P
17	Head protection with sun shade	400	4.36	.83	P
18	Pleated nose mask	400	3.30	.82	NP
19	Face mask	400	4.11	.94	P
20	Leg protector	400	4.68	.75	P

Key: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, U = Undecided, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree. Mean \geq 3.50 = P (Preferred), Mean < 3.50 = NP (Not Preferred)

Prototype Functional Protective Clothing Items

Prototype Specifications

Following the needs assessment and preference analysis, selected protective clothing options were developed into prototypes addressing common farming activities, environmental exposure, and user preferences under the humid conditions of Cross River State. The designs emphasized comfort, mobility, durability, and adaptability using locally available materials. The prototypes were produced in standard size categories and incorporated functional features to reduce exposure to farm-related hazards, as summarized in Table 3b.

Table 3b: Specifications of Prototype Functional Protective Clothing Items

Prototype Item	Material	Key Features	Size Range	Intended Hazard Coverage
Overall (with hood)	Medium-weight cotton fabric	Full body coverage, long sleeves, attached hood, front opening	S, M, L	Sun exposure, insect bites, plant scratches, dust
Overall (without hood)	Medium-weight cotton fabric	Long sleeves, full body coverage, front opening	S, M, L	Plant abrasions, soil contact, minor physical injuries
Head protector	Cotton fabric with soft foam padding	Padded crown, extended brim	Adjustable	Sun exposure, falling debris
Face/nose mask	Multi-layer cotton fabric	Pleated structure, elastic fasteners	One size	Dust, pesticide spray droplets
Hand gloves	Cotton fabric with padded palm	Reinforced palm, extended wrist length	S, M, L	Blisters, cuts, contact with tools and chemicals

Research Question 4: What are the mean ratings of judges on the appropriateness of prototype functional protective clothing for youth farmers based on fit, functional, aesthetics and expressive attributes?

Cotton fabric was selected for its breathability and comfort in humid environments, using medium-weight material to balance protection and thermal comfort. Padding was incorporated in selected areas to provide cushioning against minor impacts. Prototypes were produced in small, medium, and large sizes to accommodate variation among youth farmers and ensure ease of movement. The garments were fitted and reviewed by youth farmers and Home Economics experts, and minor adjustments were made based on feedback. Judges assessed the prototypes using a five-point rating scale. As shown in Table 4, mean ratings ranged from 3.60 to 4.70, with a cluster mean of 3.93, indicating good and satisfactory functional performance. Standard deviation values (0.61–1.21) suggest consistency in

judges' assessments of the functional attributes.

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation of responses of judges on the appropriateness of prototype functional protective clothing items on youth farmers based on functional attributes.

S/N	Appropriateness of prototype protective clothing based on functional attributes.	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remarks
1.	Comfortable for the wearer for Overall with hood	4.13	.834	A
2.	Comfortable for the wearer for Overall without hood	4.20	.561	A
3.	Comfortable for the wearer for apron with sleeve	4.30	.661	A
4.	Not irritating in wear for overall with hood	3.93	.961	A
5.	Not irritating in wear for overall without hood	4.33	.816	A
6.	Not irritating in wear for apron with sleeve	4.24	.616	A
7.	Clothing ease for overall with hood	4.07	.884	A
8.	Clothing ease for overall without hood	4.07	.704	A
9.	Clothing ease for apron with sleeve	4.07	.714	A
10.	Allow heat for the body to escape for overall with hood	3.40	1.21	A
11.	Allow heat for the body to escape for overall without hood	3.73	1.16	A
12.	Allow heat of the body to escape for apron with sleeve	3.63	1.17	A
13.	Feel on the body for overall with hood	4.13	.834	A
14.	Feel on the body for overall without hood	4.33	.488	A
15.	Feel on the body for apron with sleeve	4.53	.588	A
16.	Cool to the body for overall with hood	4.20	.941	A
17.	Cool to the body for overall without hood	4.33	.617	A
18.	Cool to the body for apron with sleeve	4.43	.618	A
19.	Free arm movement for overall with hood	3.67	.976	A
20.	Free arm movement for overall without hood	4.27	.704	A
21.	Free arm movement for apron with sleeve	4.67	.804	A
22.	Free leg movement for overall with hood	4.07	.884	A
23.	Free leg movement for overall without hood	4.27	.704	A
24.	Free leg movement for aprons with sleeve	4.20	.757	A
25.	Free torso movement for overall with hood	3.60	.737	A
26.	Free torso movement for overall without hood	4.70	.724	A
27.	Free torso movement for apron with sleeve	4.47	.712	A
28.	Ease of carrying tools for overall with hood	4.20	.941	A
29.	Ease of carrying tools for overall without hood	4.07	.884	A
30.	Ease of carrying tools for apron with sleeve	4.37	.834	A
31.	Cluster mean	3.93	.611	A

Key: 5 = Excellent, 4 = Very Good, 3 = Good, 2 = Poor, 1 = Extremely Poor

Design of protective clothing mostly preferred by youth farmers.

Figure	Image
<p>Fig. 1. Overall with hood</p> <p>The overall hood was constructed from medium-weight cotton fabric to provide full body coverage while allowing breathability in humid conditions. Key features include long sleeves, an attached hood, and a front opening for ease of wear. This design was preferred for protection against sun exposure, insect bites, vegetation scratches, and dust during tasks such as weeding, site clearing, and pesticide application.</p>	
<p>Fig. 2. Overall without hood</p> <p>This prototype provides full body coverage without a hood and allows unrestricted movement during farm work. It was preferred for its simplicity, comfort, and suitability for prolonged activities where head covering was less necessary.</p>	
<p>Fig. 3. Apron with sleeve</p> <p>The apron with sleeve was constructed from medium-weight cotton fabric to provide frontal body coverage while allowing ventilation in humid conditions. The design includes short sleeves and a protective front panel to reduce contact with soil, vegetation, and agro-chemical splashes during activities such as fertilizer application, pesticide spraying, and harvesting. This item was preferred for its balance of protection, comfort, and ease of movement during tasks that require flexibility and repeated bending.</p>	
<p>Fig. 4. Hand Gloves</p> <p>The hand gloves were constructed using cotton fabric with reinforced, padded palms and extended wrist coverage. They preferred protecting the hands against cuts, blisters, and tool contact during weeding, harvesting, and handling farm implements.</p>	
<p>Fig. 5. Head Cover</p> <p>The head cover was produced using cotton fabric with soft foam padding and an extended brim. The design offers protection against sun exposure and minor impact from falling debris and was preferred for its lightweight and comfortable fit during land clearing and harvesting.</p>	
<p>Fig. 6. Nose Mask</p> <p>The face mask was made from multi-layer cotton fabric with elastic fasteners to ensure a secure fit. It was designed to reduce exposure to dust and pesticide spray droplets and was preferred over the pleated option due to better stability during movement.</p>	

Prototype Protective Clothing Items

Assessment of functional protective clothing items by judges

Fit testing of protecting clothing items by Models

4. Discussion of Findings

The findings show that youth farmers in Cross River State engage in largely manual farming activities within a humid tropical rainforest environment characterized by dense vegetation, high rainfall, and prolonged contact with soil and plants. These conditions explain the strong preference for protective clothing that provides adequate body coverage, durability, and comfort during farm work.

Preferences for items such as overalls, gloves, head protection, and leg protection reflect the physical demands and exposure risks associated with activities like bush clearing, weeding, and harvesting, which involve contact with thorny plants, insects, reptiles, moisture, and mud. Similar

exposure risks and reliance on inadequate everyday clothing have been reported among agricultural workers in the state (Etim et al., 2021).

The demand for gloves, face masks, and head protection is also linked to increased use of fertilizers and pesticides, which expose farmers to chemical droplets and airborne particles that may irritate the skin and respiratory system (Effiong and Aboh, 2019). Lower preference for sleeveless aprons and loosely structured nose masks suggests that youth farmers prioritize full coverage and secure fit over partial or unstable designs, particularly under humid and physically demanding conditions.

Overall, the findings underscore the need for affordable, climate-appropriate farm clothing that reflects local farming practices and user preferences rather than generic protective clothing models.

4.1. Limitations of the Study

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. Data on farming activities and clothing needs were based on self-reported responses and may be influenced by recall bias or subjective perceptions. Although prototype clothing items were developed and assessed for fit and selected functional attributes, the study did not include laboratory or field-based performance testing; therefore, outcomes such as injury reduction, durability, chemical resistance, heat stress, and long-term comfort were not evaluated. Prototype assessment relied on expert and user ratings rather than extended wear-trial testing under actual farming conditions, which limits conclusions about sustained performance. In addition, the purposive selection of Local Government Areas may restrict the generalizability of the findings. Despite these limitations, the study provides design-focused evidence to support the development of locally appropriate farm clothing and informs future performance-based evaluations.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study applied a preference-based design approach to develop prototype farm clothing for youth farmers in Cross River State, Nigeria. Using a survey and research-and-development framework, farming activities and user preferences were identified and translated into functional clothing prototypes suited to local environmental and farming conditions. The study did not assess injury reduction, durability, heat stress, or productivity outcomes. Its contribution lies in demonstrating how locally informed user preferences can guide the design of functional farm clothing prototypes. The

prototypes provide a basis for further evaluation and refinement. Based on the findings, it is recommended that

1. Home Economics lecturers and curriculum planners should incorporate preference-based functional clothing design projects into relevant courses to strengthen practical skill development and address locally relevant agricultural needs.
2. Fashion designers and clothing producers should develop farm clothing designs that reflect the climatic conditions, farming activities, and economic realities of youth farmers in Cross River State, using locally available and affordable materials.
3. Future studies should conduct wear-trial evaluations of the developed prototypes to assess comfort, mobility, thermal tolerance, perceived protection, and durability during actual farm use.

Ethics Statement

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the relevant institutional authority. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to data collection. The study complied with established ethical standards for research involving human participants.

Data Availability Statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Author Contributions (CRediT)

Conceptualization and study design: Offiong, P.E., Chukwuone, C.A.; Data collection: Offiong, P.E., Gera, N.P.; Data analysis and interpretation: Offiong, P.E., Angelina, E.; Drafting of manuscript: Offiong, P.E., Chukwuone, C.A.; Critical review and editing: All authors. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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